

ADMINISTRATIVE LEADERSHIP PRACTICES AND WORK SYSTEM AT ISULAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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Administrative Leadership Practices and Work System at Isulan National High School

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Abstract

This study investigates the extent of administrative leadership practices at Isulan National High School and their impact on the work system of faculty and staff, particularly focusing on the integration of new technology. Data were collected from 114 respondents through a comprehensive survey, and the results were analyzed to determine mean scores and standard deviations for various leadership indicators. The findings reveal that the school exhibits a high level of administrative leadership, especially in integrating new technology, with a grand mean score of 4.13. This is supported by established systems, procedures, guidelines, feedback channels, and ongoing training for staff. The study also examines the overall administrative leadership practices, with mean scores for staff empowerment, quality improvement schemes, integration of new technology, and training provision being 4.08, 4.08, 4.13, and 3.96, respectively. The impact of these practices on the work system of faculty and staff was found to be significant. High mean scores were observed in goal setting (4.14), automation (4.09), communication channels (4.18), and task prioritization (4.09), indicating effective administrative influence. Additionally, a very strong positive correlation ($r = 0.884$, $p < 0.05$) was found between administrative leadership practices and the work system, highlighting that improvements in leadership practices enhance faculty and staff performance and overall school efficiency. Based on these findings, several recommendations were made: enhancing training programs for technology use, maintaining and developing existing systems, fostering a feedback culture, conducting further research on administrative leadership, and regularly monitoring and evaluating leadership practices. These recommendations aim to further improve the administrative leadership at Isulan National High School, thereby enhancing educational outcomes and work system effectiveness for faculty and staff.

Keywords: *administrative leadership practices, work system*

Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of educational institutions, the role of administrative leadership practices in shaping the work system has emerged as a critical area of inquiry. Isulan National High School, as a representative of contemporary educational settings, stands as a prime context for investigating the interplay between administrative leadership and the work system.

Administrative leadership practices encompass a spectrum of behaviors, policies, and strategies adopted by school administrators to guide, motivate, and empower faculty and staff members (Hallinger, 2020). These practices include but are not limited to decision-making processes, communication strategies, resource allocation, and organizational culture development (Leithwood et al., 2019). Effective administrative leadership not only influences the day-to-day operations of the institution but also sets the tone for fostering a culture of collaboration, innovation, and continuous improvement.

The work system within an educational institution encompasses the structures, processes, and interactions that facilitate the achievement of organizational goals and objectives (Robinson et al., 2019). This includes administrative processes, teaching methodologies, staff responsibilities, and support mechanisms. A well-functioning work system is characterized by clarity of roles, efficient workflows, effective communication channels, and alignment with the school's mission and vision (Wang & Liu, 2019).

Quantitative research methodologies offer a systematic approach to examine the relationship between administrative leadership practices and the work system at Isulan National High School. By employing survey instruments, statistical analyses, and data-driven approaches, researchers can quantify the effects of different leadership practices on various dimensions of the work system, such as staff satisfaction, productivity, and organizational effectiveness (Jones & Rudd, 2020).

Understanding the dynamics between administrative leadership practices and the work system is not only academically relevant but also holds practical implications for school administrators, policymakers, and educational stakeholders (Harris et al., 2021). By identifying the factors that contribute to an effective work system, educational institutions can devise targeted strategies to optimize administrative practices, enhance staff morale, and ultimately improve student outcomes.

Therefore, this quantitative study seeks to explore the relationship between administrative leadership practices and the work system at Isulan National High School. Through rigorous data analysis and statistical techniques, this research endeavors to provide empirical evidence to inform evidence-based decision-making and facilitate the enhancement of administrative practices to support a more effective work system at the school.

Methodology

Research Design

The quantitative-descriptive method of research was used to gather information on the reactions of respondents of faculty and staff of Isulan National High School and other relevant data in this study. A questionnaire was used in the data gathering. The study was evaluated by the respondents who are employed at Isulan National High School. As Creswell (2018) described, quantitative research tests objective theories by investigating variables' relationships. These variables can then be measured using instruments, resulting in numeric data that can be examined using statistical processes.

Participants

Slovin's Formula, through a simple random sampling technique, was used to identify the number of samples of the respondents. On the other hand, frequency count, percentage distribution, weighted mean, and correlation were utilized to analyze the responses of the one hundred fourteen faculty and staff of Isulan National High School. They were the subjects of the study. The sampling technique is reformed with a marginal error of 0.05 from the total population of 160 with a 114-sample size. These 114 respondents were distributed in the two categories of the school, where the most numbered faculty and staff are found. Lastly, study respondents are selected using a simple random sampling technique in which the researcher utilized the fishbowl method to identify the selected samples of the study. It ensures that every member of the population has an equal chance of being chosen as a study respondent.

Instruments

The research instrument is designed and administered to the respondents at Isulan National High School. It comprises sets of questions that are validated. Pre-testing is conducted to establish the tool's reliability, where Cronbach Alpha is utilized. The reliability of a test is the degree of consistency of measurement that it gives. The test is given to the individual, and after the lapse of a certain length of time, the same test is again administered to the same individual. If the scores of the two administrations are identical or almost identical, the test is reliable (Hechanova & Hechanova, 2012).

To acquire the necessary data needed for the completion of the study, a survey questionnaire was distributed to the respondents. The questionnaire will consist of three (3) sections containing questions about the respondents' demographic profile, level of administrative leadership practices at Isulan National High School, and work system. A Likert scale consisting of five options on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (neutral), 4 (Agree), and 5 (strongly agree) with corresponding quantitative descriptions will be used to measure both the level of administrative leadership practices and work system.

Procedure

In acquiring the necessary data from the respondents, the above procedures were observed. First, the researcher proposed the study through the outline defense. After the approval, the formulation of survey tools was done and went through the validation and reliability test process. The communication letters were drafted and sent to concerned agencies which are part of the study. When everything was done, the survey administration was immediately performed with the identified respondents. With the data gathered, analyzed, and interpreted, the researcher started to draft the outputs for its find presentation.

Data Analysis

To give a clear understanding of the focus and the result of the study, the following appropriate statistical treatments are applied:

A mean will be used to determine the level of administrative leadership practices and work system in Isulan National High School.

The Pearson r correlation will be used to determine the significant relationship between the administrative leadership practices and work system of Isulan National High School personnel.

The findings are presented with different tables to feature the study results thoroughly. They have discussed the gathered information by following the five-point Likert's Rating Scale, descriptive ratings, and verbal interpretations to represent the results of the research in the administrative leadership practices and work system of Isulan National High School.

Results and Discussion

The results of the data gathered during the conduct of this study. It reveals the demographic profile of faculty and staff, the extent of administrative leadership practices, and the work system. It also presents the relationship between the administrative leadership practices and work systems at Isulan National High School.

The demographic profiles of the respondents, as presented in Table 1, reveal a diverse group characterized by various attributes such as gender, educational attainment, age, marital status, professional designation, and years of service.

In terms of gender out of 114 respondents, 43.86% are male, accounting for 50 individuals, while the majority, 56.14%, are female, totaling 64 individuals. This indicates a slightly higher female representation in the respondent pool.

Table 1. Respondents' Demographic Profiles

Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	50	43.86%
Female	64	56.14%
Educational Attainment		
College Graduate	82	71.93%
Masters Degree	30	26.32%
Doctorate Degree	2	1.75%
Age		
20-25 years old	5	4.39%
26-30 years old	15	13.16%
31-35 years old	20	17.54%
36-40 years old	40	35.09%
41-45 years old	26	22.81%
46-50 years old	5	4.39%
51-55 years old	3	2.63%
Marital Status		
Single	15	13.16%
Married	93	81.58%
Widowed	6	5.26%
Position		
Teacher I	12	10.53%
Teacher II	40	35.09%
Teacher III	50	43.86%
Master Teacher I	5	4.39%
Master Teacher II	1	0.88%
ADAS II	4	3.50%
AO II	2	1.75%
No. of years in service	10	8.77%
1-5 years	35	30.70%
6-10 years	20	17.54%
11-15 years	21	18.42%
16-20 years	28	24.56%
21 years and above		
TOTAL	114	100%

In terms of educational backgrounds of the respondents show a predominant presence of college graduates, making up 71.93% (82 individuals). Those holding a master's degree constitute 26.32% (30 individuals), while a small fraction, 1.75% (2 individuals), possess a doctorate degree. This distribution reflects a well-educated group with a significant number holding advanced degrees.

In terms of age distribution spans across several age groups with the majority being within the 36-40 years old category, comprising 35.09% (40 individuals). The 26-30 years old and 41-45 years old groups follow, representing 13.16% (15 individuals) and 22.81% (26 individuals) respectively. Other age categories include 20-25 years old at 4.39% (5 individuals), 31-35 years old at 17.54% (20 individuals), 46-50 years old at 4.39% (5 individuals), and 51-55 years old at 2.63% (3 individuals). This indicates a workforce with a broad range of age groups, though skewing slightly towards the mid-career age range. In terms of marital status, a significant majority of the respondents are married, accounting for 81.58% (93 individuals). Single respondents constitute 13.16% (15 individuals), and widowed respondents make up 5.26% (6 individuals). This data suggests a predominantly married respondent demographic.

In terms of current positions, the majority are classified as Teacher II, constituting 43.86% (50 individuals). This is followed by Teacher I at 35.09% (40 individuals), Tournament Manager at 10.53% (12 individuals), Teacher III at 4.39% (5 individuals), and Master Teacher I at 0.88% (1 individual). Additionally, Master Teacher II, ADAS II, and AO II are represented by smaller proportions of 3.50% (4 individuals) and 1.75% (2 individuals) respectively. This reflects a diverse range of teaching positions and a notable number of mid-level teaching staff. In terms of number of years in service, respondents have varied lengths of tenure. Those with 6-10 years of service represent 30.70% (35 individuals), followed by 21 years and above at 24.56% (28 individuals). Individuals with 16-20 years of service account for 18.42% (21 individuals), those with 11-15 years make up 17.54% (20 individuals), and the least experienced group, with 1-5 years of service, comprises 8.77% (10 individuals). This data highlights a mix of both experienced and relatively new employees, with a significant proportion having substantial years of service.

The Extent of Administrative Leadership Practices

The extent of administrative leadership practices at Isulan National High School, Evaluating the extent of these practices helps determine their impact on the overall performance and efficiency of the institution. It encompasses various aspects such as goal setting, task prioritization, communication channels, and the integration of automation. Effective administrative leadership can enhance organizational clarity, foster collaboration, improve operational efficiency, and increase staff satisfaction, ultimately leading to a more productive and harmonious work environment.

The following tables reveal the extent of administrative leadership practices of Isulan National High School in terms of staff empowerment, training provision, quality improvement schemes, and integration of new technology.

Table 2. Extent of extent of Administrative Leadership Practices in Isulan National High School in terms of Staff Empowerment

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Systems are in place to enable faculty and staff to take responsibility for their tasks.	114	4.08	0.84	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
2. Processes exist to involve faculty and staff in decision-making activities.	114	4.09	0.75	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
3. Faculty and staff understand what is expected of them to achieve performance goals.	114	4.00	0.85	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
4. There are ways for faculty and staff to give feedback about their work.	114	4.14	0.80	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
5. There are methods to resolve conflicts among faculty and staff.	114	4.10	0.78	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
Grand Mean		4.08	0.80	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.

The data from Table 2 illustrates a consistent high extent of Administrative Leadership Practices in terms of Staff Empowerment at Isulan National High School. Across all indicators, including systems for task responsibility, involvement in decision-making, understanding of performance goals, feedback mechanisms, and conflict resolution methods, the mean scores range from 4.00 to 4.14, indicating a strong perception of established systems and effective practices among faculty and staff. With an overall Grand Mean of 4.08, it is evident that the administrative leadership fosters a conducive environment where faculty and staff feel empowered to take ownership, participate in decision-making, and provide feedback, contributing to a cohesive and productive work culture.

These findings align with existing research on effective leadership practices in educational settings. According to Leithwood and Jantzi (2008), empowering leadership fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility among faculty and staff, leading to improved performance and job satisfaction. Similarly, Hallinger and Heck (1998) emphasize the importance of involving staff in decision-making processes, which enhances their commitment and engagement. Moreover, feedback mechanisms and conflict resolution strategies, as highlighted by Avolio and Bass (2004), are crucial components of effective leadership, promoting open communication and collaboration within organizations.

Table 3. Extent of extent of Administrative Leadership Practices in Isulan National High School in terms of Training Provision

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Faculty and staff are given opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge.	114	3.99	0.79	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
2. Resources are provided for faculty and staff to participate in training programs.	114	4.13	0.67	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
3. Faculty and staff are clearly informed about the need to engage in training activities.	114	3.83	0.79	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
4. There are channels for faculty and staff to share their opinions on training programs.	114	3.87	0.72	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
5. Procedures are in place to address faculty and staff training and development needs.	114	3.98	0.76	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
Grand Mean		3.96	0.75	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.

The data presented in Table 3 illustrates a high extent of Administrative Leadership Practices concerning Training Provision at Isulan National High School. With mean scores ranging from 3.83 to 4.13, and a Grand Mean of 3.96, it is evident that faculty and staff are provided ample opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge, resources are readily available for training participation, and clear

communication exists regarding the importance of engaging in training activities. Additionally, effective channels for faculty and staff to provide feedback on training programs are in place, and procedures are established to address their training and development needs. These findings align with existing literature, which emphasizes the significance of supportive leadership in facilitating employee growth and development (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2008; Hallinger & Heck, 1998). Overall, the high mean scores indicate a positive organizational climate where training and development are prioritized, contributing to the continuous improvement and effectiveness of the school's workforce.

Table 4. *Extent of extent of Administrative Leadership Practices in Isulan National High School in terms of Quality Improvement Schemes*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Systems are established to identify areas needing quality enhancement.	114	3.99	0.90	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
2. Processes are in place to manage quality improvement issues.	114	3.98	0.85	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
3. Faculty and staff are aware of the expectations to carry out quality improvement efforts.	114	4.12	0.83	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
4. Faculty and staff have mechanisms to provide input on quality improvement activities.	114	4.12	0.82	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
5. Continuous procedures are in place for ongoing quality improvement.	114	4.18	0.84	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
Grand Mean		4.08	0.85	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.

The data presented in Table 4 offers a comprehensive glimpse into the administrative leadership practices at Isulan National High School with regards to Quality Improvement Schemes. Each indicator, from establishing systems to fostering continuous procedures, showcases a concerted effort towards enhancing educational quality. With mean scores consistently above 3.0, the findings suggest a commendable commitment from the administrative faculty and staff. This dedication to quality improvement aligns with contemporary research emphasizing the essential role of administrative leadership in shaping the educational landscape. By implementing robust systems, processes, and mechanisms for faculty input, Isulan National High School demonstrates a proactive approach to addressing areas needing enhancement and fostering a culture of ongoing improvement.

A study by Liu, et al. (2020) found that effective administrative practices, such as establishing systems, fostering awareness, and implementing continuous improvement procedures, significantly contribute to enhancing educational quality. Moreover, Jones and colleagues (2018) underscored the importance of administrative engagement and faculty input mechanisms in shaping quality improvement initiatives within schools. These findings resonate with the data from Table 8, which highlights Isulan National High School's robust administrative leadership practices aimed at quality enhancement.

Table 5. *Extent of extent of Administrative Leadership Practices in Isulan National High School in terms of Integration of New Technology*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Systems are in place to incorporate new technology into faculty and staff activities.	114	4.04	0.83	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
2. Procedures are in place to address issues related to new technology.	114	4.08	0.72	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
3. Faculty and staff have clear guidelines on how to effectively use new technology	114	4.18	0.83	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
4. There are feedback channels for faculty and staff to comment on new technology usage.	114	4.20	0.82	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to the greatest extent.
5. Ongoing training is provided to ensure staff can effectively use new technology.	114	4.17	0.75	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
Grand Mean		4.13	0.79	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.

The data presented in Table 5 provides valuable insights into the extent of Administrative Leadership Practices concerning the Integration of New Technology at Isulan National High School. Across various indicators, the mean scores consistently suggest a high level of administrative engagement and effectiveness. The presence of established systems, procedures, guidelines, feedback channels, and ongoing training underscores the proactive approach of the administrative faculty and staff towards incorporating new technology into the school's activities. With a grand mean of 4.13, it is evident that Isulan National High School places a significant emphasis on leveraging technology to enhance educational practices.

This data highlights the school's commitment to staying abreast of technological advancements and utilizing them to support teaching, learning, and administrative processes. Such findings align with contemporary research emphasizing the crucial role of administrative leadership in successfully integrating new technology in educational settings, ultimately contributing to improved student outcomes and organizational effectiveness.

A study by Chen et al. (2021) found that establishing clear guidelines and feedback mechanisms for staff significantly contributes to the successful adoption and utilization of new technology. Similarly, Liu and colleagues (2019) emphasized the importance of ongoing training and support for faculty to ensure their effective use of technology in teaching and administrative tasks. These findings resonate with the data from Table 6, which highlights Isulan National High School's robust administrative leadership practices in integrating new technology. Thus, the school's proactive approach aligns with contemporary research emphasizing the critical role of administrative leadership in navigating technological advancements and harnessing them to enhance educational practices.

Table 6. *Summary of the Extent of Administrative Leadership Practices in Isulan National High School*

Hard Infrastructure Projects	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
Staff Empowerment	4.08	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
Quality Improvement Schemes	4.08	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
Integration of New Technology	4.13	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.
Training Provision	3.96	The administrative faculty and staff practice administrative leadership to a high extent.

Table 6 provides a summary of the extent of Administrative Leadership Practices at Isulan National High School, reflecting a consistent and high level of administrative engagement across various domains. For administrative leadership practices, the mean score of 4.08 indicates that staff empowerment is practiced to a high extent. Similarly, the provision of training has a mean score of 3.96, suggesting strong administrative leadership in this area as well. Quality improvement schemes also score highly with a mean of 4.08, further demonstrating the school's commitment to continuous improvement. The integration of new technology receives the highest mean score of 4.13, highlighting a particularly robust focus on leveraging technological advancements. Overall, these scores illustrate that Isulan National High School maintains a comprehensive and effective administrative leadership framework, ensuring continuous improvement and adaptation. These findings align with recent research emphasizing the essential role of administrative leadership in fostering educational quality and technological integration (Chen et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019).

It also reveals that the highest-rated administrative leadership practices at Isulan National High School are the integration of new technology and staff empowerment, both receiving mean scores of 4.13 and 4.08 respectively, indicating these practices are implemented to a high extent by the administrative faculty and staff. In contrast, the lowest-rated practice is training provision, which has a mean score of 3.96. Despite being the lowest, this score still reflects a high extent of practice. Overall, these results highlight a strong emphasis on integrating new technology and empowering staff, while also maintaining a solid commitment to providing training.

The findings at Isulan National High School, where the integration of new technology and staff empowerment scored the highest with mean scores of 4.13 and 4.08 respectively, align with existing literature on effective administrative practices. Liu and Szabo (2009) highlight that successful technology integration enhances administrative efficiency and supports innovative teaching, which is reflected in the high score for this practice. Similarly, Bogler and Somech (2004) emphasize that empowering staff leads to increased motivation and professional growth, which aligns with the strong emphasis on staff empowerment observed at the school.

Level of Effects of Administrative Leadership Practices in the Work System of Faculty and Staff

A work system encompasses the processes, procedures, and tools used by an organization to achieve its goals. It includes the tasks performed, the people involved, the technologies employed, and the information utilized. In educational institutions, an effective work system ensures that faculty and staff can efficiently and collaboratively meet organizational objectives. The tables below present the level of impact of administrative leadership practices on the work system of faculty and staff.

Table 7 illustrates the effects of Administrative Leadership Practices on the work system of faculty and staff at Isulan National High School, particularly in terms of goal setting. The data reveals consistently high mean scores across all indicators, suggesting a strong administrative influence on goal-setting processes. Specifically, there are clear processes in place for setting goals, with a mean score

of 4.15 and a standard deviation of 0.77, indicating that faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system understanding. Faculty and staff involvement in the goal-setting process is also rated highly, with a mean of 4.20 and a standard deviation of 0.81, reflecting an excellent level of engagement. Goals are clearly defined, and staff understand expectations well, as shown by the highest mean score of 4.24 and a standard deviation of 0.84, denoting an excellent level of clarity and understanding.

Table 7. *Effects of Administrative Leadership Practices in the Work System of Faculty and Staff in terms of Goal Setting*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. There are clear processes in place for setting goals.	114	4.15	0.77	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
2. Faculty and staff are involved in the goal-setting process through established procedures.	114	4.20	0.81	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of work system
3. Goals are clearly defined, faculty and staff understand the expectations for achieving them.	114	4.24	0.84	The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of work system
4. There are feedback systems to evaluate the achievement of goals.	114	4.07	0.82	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
5. Procedures are in place for addressing goal-related issues.	114	4.04	0.78	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
Grand Mean		4.14	0.80	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system

Feedback systems for evaluating goal achievement are effective, with a mean score of 4.07 and a standard deviation of 0.82, illustrating a high level of systematic feedback integration. Additionally, procedures for addressing goal-related issues are robust, with a mean score of 4.04 and a standard deviation of 0.78, maintaining a high level of procedural effectiveness. The grand mean of 4.14 with a standard deviation of 0.80 underscores the overall high level of administrative leadership in facilitating an effective work system for faculty and staff through well-defined goal-setting processes. These findings align with recent research that emphasizes the importance of clear goal-setting and systematic feedback in enhancing faculty and staff performance (Chen et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019).

Table 8. *Effects of Administrative Leadership Practices in the Work System of Faculty and Staff in terms of Automation*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Clear processes are established for automating tasks and workflows.	114	4.15	0.78	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
2. Procedures exist to prioritize which tasks should be automated.	114	4.05	0.80	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
3. Faculty and staff understand the expectations for using automated systems	114	4.04	0.75	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
4. Feedback mechanisms are in place to assess the effectiveness of automated systems.	114	4.06	0.82	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
5. There are procedures to address issues arising from automation.	114	4.15	0.80	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
Grand Mean		4.09	0.79	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system

Table 8 examines the effects of Administrative Leadership Practices on the work system of faculty and staff at Isulan National High School, specifically regarding automation. The data reveals high mean scores across various indicators, such as clear processes for automating tasks and workflows (mean = 4.15), procedures to prioritize automation (mean = 4.05), understanding expectations for using automated systems (mean = 4.04), feedback mechanisms for assessing effectiveness (mean = 4.06), and procedures to address automation issues (mean = 4.15). With a grand mean of 4.09, the results indicate a high level of work system effectiveness facilitated by strong administrative leadership.

These findings align with contemporary research highlighting the importance of effective administrative leadership in integrating automation to enhance operational efficiency and staff satisfaction. Studies by Johnson et al. (2020) and Smith and Jones (2018) emphasize that clear processes, prioritization, feedback mechanisms, and continuous improvement are critical for successful automation in educational settings. This underscores the significant role of administrative leadership in optimizing work systems and leveraging technology to improve overall performance.

Table 9 examines the influence of Administrative Leadership Practices on the work system of faculty and staff at Isulan National High School, specifically focusing on communication channels. The data reveals consistently high mean scores across various indicators,

indicating a robust administrative impact on communication strategies within the institution. Key findings include clear methods for effective communication, active involvement of faculty and staff in planning communication strategies, well-defined communication expectations, established feedback mechanisms for evaluation, and procedures for addressing communication-related issues. With a grand mean of 4.18, the results underscore an overall high level of work system effectiveness, highlighting the importance of strong administrative leadership in fostering clear and efficient communication practices.

Table 9. *Effects of Administrative Leadership Practices in the Work System of Faculty and Staff in terms of Communication Channels*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Clear methods are established for effective communication with faculty and staff.	114	4.18	0.72	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
2. Faculty and staff are involved in planning communication strategies through set procedures.	114	4.17	0.80	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system The faculty and staff exhibit an excellent level of work system
3. Communication expectations are clearly defined for all faculty and staff.	114	4.29	0.78	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
4. Feedback mechanisms are established for evaluating communication.	114	4.13	0.83	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
5. Procedures are in place for addressing communication-related issues.	114	4.14	0.72	
Grand Mean		4.18	0.77	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system

This aligns with contemporary research emphasizing the pivotal role of effective communication channels in educational leadership. For instance, Smith, Jones, and Davis (2020) conducted a case study analysis and found that clear communication methods significantly enhance organizational effectiveness in educational settings. Similarly, Brown, Johnson, and Garcia (2019) highlighted the importance of communication in educational leadership through a systematic review, emphasizing its role in fostering collaboration and improving employee satisfaction. These studies underscore the significance of strong administrative leadership in fostering clear and efficient communication practices, ultimately contributing to organizational success and employee well-being.

Table 10. *Effects of Administrative Leadership Practices in the Work System of Faculty and Staff in terms of Task Prioritization*

Indicator	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Clear processes are established for prioritizing tasks and projects.	114	4.18	0.82	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
2. Faculty and staff are included in the task prioritization process through set procedures.	114	4.10	0.73	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
3. Expectations for achieving prioritized tasks are clearly communicated	114	4.11	0.76	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
4. Feedback mechanisms are established for evaluating task priorities.	114	4.00	0.84	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
5. There are procedures to address issues related to task prioritization.	114	4.08	0.86	
Grand Mean		4.09	0.80	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system

Table 10 presents an analysis of the effects of Administrative Leadership Practices on the work system of faculty and staff at Isulan National High School, specifically focusing on task prioritization. The data reveals consistently high mean scores across various indicators, indicating a robust administrative influence on task prioritization processes within the institution.

Firstly, clear processes are established for prioritizing tasks and projects, as reflected by a mean score of 4.18 and a standard deviation of 0.82, suggesting a high level of clarity and effectiveness in task prioritization methods. Faculty and staff inclusion in the task prioritization process through set procedures is also rated highly, with a mean score of 4.10 and a standard deviation of 0.73, indicating active participation in determining task priorities.

Furthermore, expectations for achieving prioritized tasks are clearly communicated, with a mean score of 4.11 and a standard deviation of 0.76, demonstrating a high level of clarity and alignment regarding task expectations. Feedback mechanisms for evaluating task priorities are established, as shown by a mean score of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.84, reflecting a proactive approach to assessing and adjusting task priorities based on feedback.

Lastly, procedures are in place to address issues related to task prioritization, with a mean score of 4.08 and a standard deviation of 0.86, ensuring a systematic approach to resolving prioritization challenges. The grand mean of 4.09 and a standard deviation of 0.80 indicate an overall high level of work system effectiveness among faculty and staff, facilitated by strong administrative leadership in task prioritization practices.

This aligns with existing literature emphasizing the crucial role of effective task prioritization in organizational success. For instance, a study by Johnson et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of clear processes and procedures for prioritizing tasks, which significantly enhance organizational productivity and efficiency. Similarly, Smith and Jones (2020) underscored the value of including faculty and staff in the task prioritization process, as it fosters a sense of ownership and accountability among team members. Moreover, research by Brown et al. (2018) emphasized the significance of clear communication and feedback mechanisms in task prioritization, ensuring alignment with organizational goals and objectives.

These findings align with existing literature emphasizing the crucial role of effective task prioritization in organizational success. Johnson et al. (2019) and Smith and Jones (2020) highlight the importance of clear processes and procedures, faculty and staff inclusion, and clear communication and feedback mechanisms in task prioritization. Brown et al. (2018) emphasize the significance of these factors in ensuring alignment with organizational goals and objectives. Strong administrative leadership in task prioritization practices is essential for achieving high work system effectiveness and contributing to organizational success.

Table 11. *Summary on the Effects of Administrative Leadership Practices on the Work System of Faculty and Staff*

Status of ARB's	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
Goal Setting	4.14	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
Automation	4.09	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system
Communication Channels	4.18	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system.
Task Prioritization	4.09	The faculty and staff exhibit a high level of work system.

Table 11 summarizes the effects of Administrative Leadership Practices on the work system of faculty and staff at Isulan National High School across various domains. The mean scores indicate consistently high levels of effectiveness in each area, with qualitative descriptions affirming the faculty and staff's high level of work system across all domains.

In terms of goal setting, the mean score of 4.14 suggests that clear processes and expectations are in place, fostering a high level of alignment and understanding among faculty and staff (Hallinger & Heck, 1996). Similarly, in the realm of automation, the mean score of 4.09 indicates that administrative leadership has facilitated a seamless integration of automated systems, enhancing operational efficiency (Brown et al., 2018).

Communication channels also exhibit a high level of effectiveness, as evidenced by the mean score of 4.18. This suggests that clear methods and expectations for communication have been established, fostering effective collaboration and information flow among faculty and staff (Johnson et al., 2019). Lastly, in the area of task prioritization, the mean score of 4.09 reflects a strong administrative influence in ensuring that tasks are effectively prioritized and aligned with organizational goals (Smith & Jones, 2020).

The Analysis of Administrative Leadership Practices and Work System

The effectiveness of administrative leadership practices is crucial for the performance and efficiency of work systems in educational settings. To investigate this relationship at Isulan National High School, a statistical analysis was conducted to determine the correlation between these two variables. Table 12 provides an overview of this relationship, highlighting the strength and significance of the correlation. The findings offer insights into how improvements in administrative leadership can enhance the overall work system, thereby supporting the institution's operational success.

Table 12 discuss the analysis of the relationship between the variables "administrative leadership practices" and "worksytem" reveals a very strong positive correlation, as indicated by a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.884. This high correlation coefficient suggests that there is a strong linear relationship between the two variables, meaning that as the value of "administrative leadership practices" increases, the value of "worksytem" tends to increase as well.

The significance of this correlation was assessed using a two-tailed test with a significance level of 0.05. The resulting p-value for the correlation between "administrative leadership practices" and "worksytem" is 0.000. Since this p-value is well below the 0.05 threshold, we can conclude that the correlation is statistically significant. This implies that the observed relationship between "administrative leadership practices" and "worksytem" is highly unlikely to be due to random chance, thereby affirming the reliability of the correlation in this context.

Table 12. *Degree of Relationship Between Administrative Leadership Practices and Work System*

Pair of Variable	n	R	P-value
Administrative Leadership Practices and Work System	114	0.884**	0.000

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level of significance

These results are based on a sample size of 114 observations, providing a robust dataset for the analysis. The strong and significant correlation suggests that there is a meaningful relationship between the administrative leadership practices and the work system under study, which could be a key insight for further research and practical applications in this field.

In the context of this dissertation, these findings align with prior research indicating the importance of administrative factors in influencing work system efficiency (Smith, 2020; Johnson, 2019). The significant correlation underscores the potential impact of administrative improvements on enhancing work system performance, supporting the hypotheses proposed in this study.

Conclusions

Based on these findings, several conclusions can be drawn: Firstly, Isulan National High School demonstrates a high level of administrative leadership in integrating new technology, empowering staff, and implementing quality improvement schemes, fostering an effective and innovative educational environment. Secondly, effective administrative leadership practices significantly enhance the work system of faculty and staff, as evidenced by clear goal-setting processes, automation, effective communication channels, and task prioritization. Thirdly, while the provision of training is rated highly, it is the lowest among the evaluated practices, suggesting a need for continuous improvement and possibly more frequent or comprehensive training programs to keep up with technological advancements. Lastly, the very strong positive correlation between administrative leadership practices and the work system indicates that leadership improvements can directly enhance faculty and staff performance and overall school efficiency.

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